

Investigations on the phytoplankton composition and trophic status of Lake Karagöl (Dikili-İzmir-Türkiye)

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Abstract

The phytoplankton composition, TN:TP ratios as the limiting factor on phytoplankton and the trophic Status of Lake Karagöl, a small volcanic-originated lake, were first investigated in this study. Additionally, the physicochemical parameters of the lake were measured. As a result of the investigations, 21 dominant taxa from four divisions among phytoplanktonic organisms were identified in Karagöl. Three taxa belonged to Cyanobacteria, eleven to Chlorophyta, six to Ochrophyta (only Bacillariophyceae), and to one to Myzozoa. The average depth of the lake was calculated as 8.7 m. In line with the atmospheric temperatures brought by the Mediterranean climate prevailing in the region, surface water temperatures of the lake fluctuated between 23.0 °C (summer) and 6.5 °C (winter). Conductivity ranged from 780 to 423 µS and dissolved oxygen ranged from 15.3 to 7.3 mg l⁻¹. The average scores of TSI (SD), TSI (Chl-a), TSI (TN) and TSI (TP) were calculated as 68.0, 55.1, 62.1 and 86.4 respectively. These TSI scores indicated that Lake Karagöl was at eutrophic or hypereutrophic levels. TN:TP ratio of the lake ranged from 9.8 to 7.2 and in this case, the Lake Karagöl food chain is nitrogen-limited because of the low TN:TP ratios. *Dolichospermum flosaquae* (N₂-fixing heterocystous Cyanobacteria) was the dominant species in Lake Karagöl phytoplankton during the summer months when the high-water temperature. As a result of this study, based on phytoplankton composition, dominant algae groups (especially Cyanobacteria) and TSI scores, it was evaluated that Lake Karagöl (Dikili) has suitable environmental conditions for many algae species found in mesotrophic and eutrophic lakes and is in a very rapidly progressing hypertrophication process.

Introduction

Small lakes, typically stagnant water bodies with surface areas ranging from a few acres to several hectares, host highly diverse floristic and faunistic communities. These lakes serve as vital habitats for a variety of aquatic organisms such as fish, amphibians and invertebrates, and also contribute to the conservation of local biodiversity by

supporting populations of waterfowl and other birds (Schafft et al., 2023; Labat et al., 2022; Biggs et al., 2017). In addition, these lakes, which are recreation areas because they offer opportunities such as fishing, boating, swimming and nature observation, contribute to the physical and mental health of local people, as well as providing numerous ecological, social and economic benefits

(Meyerhoff et al., 2022). Although the protection and management of these valuable aquatic ecosystems have the potential to provide sustainable contributions to the well-being of current and future generations, until recently research on the ecology or hydrobiology of small lakes has lagged that of large lakes (Downing, 2010). Due to their limited morphometry, they exhibit complex ecological dynamics affected by factors such as water depth, nutrient availability and surrounding land use, and are highly sensitive to pressures such as anthropogenic pollution, habitat modification and climate change (Koff et al., 2016; Winslow et al., 2015).

Phytoplankton as communities of microscopic algae, are important primary producers in lake ecosystems and the basis of the aquatic food web because of using sunlight and nutrients for photosynthesis (Reynolds, 2006). Their abundance and diversity serve as crucial indicators of water quality and ecosystem health (Padišák et al., 2006). According to the literature search, curiosity about understanding the driving factors of regulating the spatial and temporal phytoplankton distribution and their functional assemblages of small and shallow lakes started to increase in the early 2000s. (O'Farrell et al., 2003; Ortega-Mayagoitia et al., 2003; Padišák et al., 2003; Stoyneva, 2003). In the following years, studies on the phytoplankton communities, other primary producers, trophic conditions, and ecology of these lakes have also risen in our country (Çelekli et al., 2007; Soyulu and Gönülol, 2006; Taş et al., 2010; Altınışçılı et al., 2014; Taş, 2012). When these studies from the past to present are examined, it is evaluated that the most characteristic problem of these valuable and sensitive aquatic habitats is mostly pollution, and the most common result of this is the eutrophication phenomenon. Global warming and its negative effects on lakes also play a booster role in this dramatic process (Kosten et al., 2012). The Total Nitrogen and Total Phosphorus ratio (TN:TP) is a pivotal factor influencing eutrophication dynamics in water bodies (Smith et al., 1999). This ratio serves as a crucial indicator of nutrient availability, with imbalances often leading to excessive algal growth (especially Cyanobacterial bloom) and subsequent oxygen depletion (Jeppesen et al., 2005; Conley et al.,

2009; Frenken, 2023). Such nutrient-driven eutrophication can profoundly impact water quality and ecosystem health (Paerl and Paul, 2012), emphasizing the necessity for effective nutrient management strategies to maintain balanced TN:TP ratios and mitigate eutrophication risks (Elser et al. 2007). Moreover, the Trophic Status Index (TSI) is a critical tool for swiftly evaluating the nutrient levels and ecological health of lakes. Through the analysis of parameters such as nutrient concentrations and chlorophyll levels, TSI provides a concise assessment of a lake's trophic status, facilitating informed management decisions to uphold water quality and ecological equilibrium (Carlson, 1977).

The aims of this study were to reveal preliminary knowledge of the phytoplankton composition, to determine the limiting factor on phytoplankton by calculating TN:TP ratios, and to evaluate the Trophic Status of this small lake (Lake Karagöl).

Materials and Methods

Study area and sampling

Lake Karagöl (38°57'29"N 26°50'55"E) is located at an altitude of 430 m above sea level and 2.5 km away from the Aegean Sea shores as the crow flies' distance within the borders of the Dikili District of Izmir in Western Anatolia. (Figure 1). Karagöl is a small lake with a surface area of approximately 3.5 ha and it is known that the lake was formed as a result of volcanic activities. Four different eruption phases were distinguished within the volcanic piles on the Kardağ Mountain, where the lake is located, and it was reported that due to the spread of lava flows away from the center of the lake, the origin of the explosion was the lake pit, and this stagnant water structure was a volcanic lake (Karacık et al., 2007). Agricultural and livestock activities were observed near the lake. Biological and water sampling were made seasonally from a single point determined in the lake between 2012 and 2013 years. Phytoplankton sampling was carried out using a Hydrobios plankton net with a 55 µm mesh size and drawing circles for 15 minutes. The collected phytoplankton samples were fixed with formaldehyde to a final concentration of 4%. Prefiltered (60 µm) surface water samples were stored in polyethylene jars (1 L volume) and then taken to the laboratory in freezers to protect them

from atmospheric effects. The water samples for chlorophyll *a* analysis were collected into 200-mL amber-glass bottles.

Figure 1. Study location and sampling point

Identification and physicochemical analysis

Monograph-level key books of various researchers were used in the identification of phytoplankton species (Huber-Pestalozzi, 1941, 1942; Philipose, 1967; Sims, 1996; Komárek & Anagnostidis, 1999; John et al., 2003; Komárek & Zapomelova, 2007). The current positions of the identified taxa in the systematic hierarchy were checked on the algaebase.org website (Guiry & Guiry, 2014). All the species identifications were made using an Olympus BX53 upright microscope (Olympus Corporation, Japan).

Measurements of temperature, light penetration (with 30 cm Ø black/white Secchi disk), dissolved oxygen (with WTW Oxi 330) and electrical conductivity (with YSI 30 model SCT meter) from the physicochemical properties of water were carried out in situ. HACH LANGE spectrometric test kits [Total Nitrogen (Koroleff digestion+ 2,6-dimethylphenol method with LCK 138 range: 1-16 mg/L TN), Total Phosphorus (Phosphomolybdenum blue methods with LCK 348 range: 0.5-5.0 mg/L PO₄-P)] were used to analyze the chemical properties of water samples. Analyzes were made with a HACH LANGE DR

2800 model Spectrophotometer and HACH LANGE BRB 200 Thermoreactor (for Total Nitrogen). The fluorometric method (Madden & Day, 1992) was used to determine chlorophyll-*a* concentrations (10 AU Model Turner Designs fluorometer). The Trophic State Index (TSI) method was used to determine the trophic level of the lake. Index results were calculated using the values of Secchi depth, Chlorophyll-*a*, TP and TN concentrations to the formulas given respectively (Kratzer & Brezonik, 1981; Carlson and Simpson, 1996): $TSI (SD) = 60 - 14.41 \ln(SD)$ (SD :Secchi Depth ,m); $TSI (Chl-a) = 9,81 \ln(Chl-a) + 30,6$ (Chl-*a* : Chlorophyll-*a*, $\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$); $TSI (TP) = 14.42 \ln TP + 4.1$ (TP: Total Phosphorus, $\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$); $TSI(TN) = 54.45 + 14.43 \ln(TN)$ (Total Nitrogen mg l^{-1}).

Results and Discussion

As a result of the algological examinations, 21 dominant taxa from four divisions among phytoplanktonic organisms were identified in Karagöl. Three taxa belonged to Cyanobacteria, eleven to Chlorophyta, six to Ochrophyta (only Bacillariophyceae), and to one to Myzozoa. (Figure 2).

Figure 2. The distribution of phytoplankton divisions and number of taxa by seasons

Dominantly observed phytoplankton species and their seasonal compositions in Lake Karagöl are listed in Table 1. Cyanobacteria (blue-green algae) members were detected more commonly in eutrophic lakes in our country (Cirik-Altındağ, 1982; Gönülol & Çomak, 1992; Albay et al., 2003; Sömek & Balık, 2009), and the members of this section were found to be abundant in nutrient-rich and eutrophic lakes in the summer months (Vaitomaa, 2006). During this research, very few taxa from Cyanobacteria were identified, but when their density was evaluated, they were found to be relatively dominant in phytoplankton in summer. In a study conducted on the processes regulating the dominance of planktonic diatoms and cyanobacteria in several eutrophic lakes, it was found that diatoms and, to a lesser extent, Chlorophyta species were dominant in periods when water temperature (<15 °C) and water column stability were low, and in periods when water temperature and water column stability were high. It has been reported that cyanobacteria are dominant (Zhang and Prepas, 1996). When the seasonal change of phytoplankton of Karagöl (Dikili) was examined, an analogous phytoplankton dynamic was observed.

The Chlorophyta (green algae) division was the phytoplankton group represented by the highest number of taxa in our research area. The entire Chlorophyta division consisted of Chlorococcales members. This pattern is like the phytoplankton

composition of many mesotrophic and eutrophic lakes in our country. (Gönülol & Obalı, 1998; İşbakan-Taş et al., 2002; Ongun-Sevindik, 2010). The presence of Chlorococcales members was reported as a transition from the oligotrophic level to the eutrophic level (Hutchinson, 1957). It is known that species belonging to the *Monoraphidium* genus are dominant in oligotrophic and mesotrophic lakes (Legnerova, 1965). *Scenedesmus* and *Pediastrum* species, which are other Chlorococcales members frequently found in current study area, were frequently encountered in oligomesotrophic reservoirs and eutrophic lakes in our country (İşbakan-Taş et al., 2002; Kıvrak & Gürbüz, 2005; Ongun-Sevindik, 2010). Desmids, another group of green algae whose species are found in many oligotrophic and mesotrophic lakes in our country (Akgöz & Güler, 2004; Baykal et al., 2004; Karacaoğlu et al., 2004), were not observed in Lake Karagöl (Dikili). Palmer (1980) reported that most Desmidiaceae species can be found in oligotrophic water bodies, and a few in eutrophic water bodies.

As a result of the examinations, diatoms (Bacillariophyceae) in phytoplankton were the second most dominant group after the members of the Chlorophyta division. It has been reported that the pelagic species, *Ulnaria ulna* (Nitzsch) Compère, which was frequently detected in our research area, is one of the characteristic species of eutrophic lakes (Hustedt, 1930, 1945; Reynolds et

al., 2002). Centric diatoms are algal groups that are best adapted to systems that are rich in nutritious mineral substances and have high turbidity (Izaguirre et al., 2001). Species of the *Aulacoseira* and *Cyclotella* species were observed in Lake Karagöl (Dikili) in the autumn phytoplankton, where water column stability was disrupted and mixing increased. Species originating from benthic were also identified among the diatom members in the lake (*Gomphonema olivaceum* (Hornemann) Ehrenberg, *Pinnularia maior* (Kützing) Rabenhorst). It is known that pennate diatoms of benthic origin are transported to the pelagic region due to various water movements in

relatively shallow, small-area lakes and ponds (Round, 1973). Similar situations were reported in the lakes of our country (Şen et al., 2001; Akgöz & Güler, 2004). Most of the Bacillariophyceae members identified in this research have a high tolerance to environmental variables and are widely distributed in many lakes and other water bodies at different trophic levels in our country (Aysel, 2005). In our research area, only *Peridiniopsis cunningtonii* Lemmermann species from the Myzozoa (Dinoflagellates) was identified. *P. cunningtonii* is also found in mesotrophic or eutrophic inland water ecosystems in Türkiye (Sömek et al., 2005; Ongun-Sevindik, 2010).

Table 1. Dominant phytoplankton species and seasonal composition of Lake Karagöl

	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter
Cyanobacteria				
<i>Dolichospermum floasaquae</i> (Brébisson ex Bornet & Flahault) P.Wacklin, L.Hoffmann & J.Komárek		+	+	
<i>Merismopedia minima</i> G.Beck				+
<i>Limnothrix</i> sp.		+		+
Chlorophyta				
<i>Actinastrum hantzschii</i> Lagerheim	+			
<i>Botryococcus braunii</i> Kützing	+	+	+	
<i>Desmodesmus communis</i> (E.Hegewald) E.Hegewald	+		+	
<i>Desmodesmus opoliensis</i> (P.G.Richter) E.Hegewald	+		+	
<i>Golenkinia radiata</i> Chodat	+			
<i>Micractinium pusillum</i> Fresenius	+			+
<i>Monoraphidium griffithii</i> (Berkeley) Komárková-Legnerová	+			
<i>Monoraphidium irregulare</i> (G.M.Smith) Komárková-Legnerová	+		+	
<i>Pseudopediastrum boryanum</i> (Turpin) E.Hegewald	+	+	+	+
<i>Scenedesmus obliquus</i> (Turpin) Kützing	+		+	
<i>Tetraëdron minimum</i> (A.Braun) Hansgirg	+		+	
Ochrophyta (Bacillariophyceae)				
<i>Aulacoseira italica</i> (Ehrenberg) Simonsen	+			
<i>Cyclotella meneghiniana</i> Kützing	+			
<i>Gomphonema olivaceum</i> (Hornemann) Brébisson	+			+
<i>Nitzschia acicularis</i> (Kützing) W.Smith	+	+	+	
<i>Pinnularia maior</i> (Kützing) Cleve	+		+	+
<i>Ulnaria ulna</i> (Nitzsch) P.Compère	+	+	+	
Myzozoa				
<i>Peridiniopsis cunningtonii</i> Lemmermann			+	

Physicochemical parameters measured in Karagöl are given in detail in Table 2. During the study, no dramatic changes were observed in the depth of the lake and the average depth was calculated as 8.7 m. In line with the atmospheric temperatures brought by the Mediterranean climate prevailing in the region, surface water temperatures of the lake

fluctuated between 23.0 °C (summer) and 6.5 °C (winter). Conductivity ranged from 780 to 423 µS and dissolved oxygen ranged from 15.3 to 7.3 mg l⁻¹, according to, Turkish Surface Water Quality Regulation (SWQR, 2016), the quality of Lake Karagöl surface water was class II (good) and class I (very good), respectively. Carlson's Trophic

State Index (TSI), developed by Robert G. Carlson, is a method used to evaluate and classify the trophic state of freshwater bodies such as lakes and reservoirs, based on measurements of chlorophyll-a concentration, total phosphorus and Secchi disk transparency (Carlson, 1977). The classification of freshwater bodies according to TSI values ranges from oligotrophic (TSI < 40) to hypereutrophic (TSI > 70), with mesotrophic (TSI 40-50) and eutrophic (TSI 50-70) classifications in between. Secchi depth (SD), Chlorophyll *a* (Chl-*a*), Total Nitrogen (TN) and Total Phosphorus (TP) values were used to generate the Carlson Trophic State Index scores. The average scores of TSI (SD), TSI (Chl-*a*), TSI (TN) and TSI (TP) were calculated as 68.0, 55.1, 62.1 and 86.4 respectively. These TSI scores indicated that Lake Karagöl was at eutrophic or hypereutrophic levels. The TN:TP ratio is a key approach frequently used to analyze the dynamics of lake ecosystems (van

Wijk et al., 2024). It has been reported that nitrogen is limiting when the TN:TP ratio is <10, phosphorus is limiting when the TN:TP ratio is >17, and freshwater ecosystems are balanced when the TN:TP ratio is between 10-17 (Smith, 1983). TN:TP ratio of the lake ranged from 9.8 to 7.2 and in this case, the Lake Karagöl food chain is nitrogen-limited because of the low TN:TP ratios. It has been observed in the studies that the blooms of N₂-fixing (heterocystous blue-green algae) cyanobacteria can be supported by low TN:TP ratios or N-limited conditions (Moisander et al, 2012; González-Madina et al., 2019). This succession dynamic was confirmed by the presence of *Dolichospermum flosoaquae* (Bornet & Flahault) P.Wacklin, L.Hoffmann & Komárek as the dominant species in Lake Karagöl phytoplankton during the summer months when the high-water temperature.

Table 2. Physicochemical parameters and Carlson's TSI values of Lake Karagöl

PARAMETERS	Mean	Maximum	Minimum	TSI_Mean	TSI_Max	TSI_Min
Depth (m)	8.7	10.0	8.1	-	-	-
Temperature (°C)	14.8	23.0	6.5	-	-	-
Conductivity (25°C) µS	497.2	780	423	-	-	-
Dissolved Oxygen (mg l ⁻¹)	9.6	15.3	7.3	-	-	-
Secchi Depth (m)	0.58	0.70	0.35	** 68.0	*** 75.1	** 65.1
Chlorophyll <i>a</i> (µg l ⁻¹)	12.2	21.2	6.8	** 55.1	** 60.5	* 49.4
TN (µg l ⁻¹)	2846	4580	1400	** 62.1	** 66.7	** 58.2
TP (µg l ⁻¹)	300	466	195	*** 86.4	*** 92.7	*** 80.2
TN:TP Ratio	9.5	9.8	7.2	N limitation	N limitation	N limitation

(*mesotrophic, **eutrophic, ***hypertrophic)

Conclusions

As a result of the study, it was evaluated that Lake Karagöl (Dikili) is eutrophic or hypereutrophic based on phytoplankton composition, dominant algae groups (especially Cyanobacteria), and TSI scores and so environmental conditions of the lake were suitable for many algae species commonly observed in nutrient-rich inland waters of the world. For this reason, the authors have predicted that Lake Karagöl (Dikili), which is the drainage

area of the land it's around, was partially affected by the agricultural and livestock activities nearby.

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Ethical approval

The author declares that this study complies with research and publication ethics.

Informed consent

Not available.

Conflicts of interest

There is no conflict of interests for publishing their study.

Data availability statement

The authors declare that data are available from authors upon reasonable request.

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Author contribution

Haşım Sömek: Writing original draft, Conceptualization, Sampling, Species identification.

Esat Tarık Topkara: Project administration, Investigation, Analysis, Review, Editing.

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